

TO LEARN THE DURABILITY OF MOLDS WHEN MAKING DETAILS ON THE BASIS OF STAMPING IN A COLD CASE

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the methods of stamping metals, studying the durability of stamping molds in cold condition.

Mold in applied art a special device used for casting and printing decorative patterns; andaza. Carved flower yarn is used to print flowers on fabric; a form of wood or plaster used in casting copper; brick used by the jeweler to create ornaments on the surface of jewelry. When casting ganch ornaments, koshin is a decoration made of rivets. The stamping process is a method of processing metal, which leads to the deformation of the metal plastic, the use of mold and stamping equipment to plate pressure, the deformation or separation of the plastic from which the plate is made, so that the parts have a certain shape, size and performance.

Features: Stamping is a processing method with high production efficiency and low material consumption. The stamping process is used in the production of a large number of parts and products, easy to mechanize and automate, has high

production efficiency, however, stamping production can only strive to consume less waste and produce waste, and in some cases even excess materials are available and can be fully utilized. The operation process is convenient and does not require a high level of skill from the operator. Stamping parts usually do not require machining and have greater dimensional accuracy. The stamping parts have good interchangeability. The stability of the stamping process is good, the stamping parts are the same. It can be installed and replaced without affecting the performance of the product. Because the stamping parts are made of plate, its surface quality is improved, which creates favorable conditions for subsequent processing processes (such as electroplating and spray painting). Stamping can have high strength, great hardness and light parts. The mass of stamping parts produced by the mold is cheap. Stamping can produce parts with

complex shapes, which are difficult to process with other metal processing methods. Volumetric stamping is usually heated to a certain temperature the so-called stamp of metal billets (usually consisting of two phases which is) poured into the groove of the lower stage of the instrument and struck with the upper stage is said to deform during operation and fill the stamp cavity. This method is more efficient than the free hammer known above height, intricate shapes, shapes and sizes accuracy, low surface roughness, requires a highly skilled worker. Many homogeneous cleansers are made according to their advantages widely used in large blacksmith shops. But the value of the stamp price, The disadvantage of this method is that the cleaning mass is from 250 to 300 kg is. Small series details stamp is much more expensive to obtain.

So here are some ways to stamp can be used.

1. Mechanical stamping;
2. Hydraulic stamping;
3. Explosive stamping;
4. According to the elements of preparation stamping

Rubber stamping is done on crooked stamping presses, mainly non-ferrous metals and alloys up to 2 mm thick, low carbon steel sheets, non-ferrous metals can be stamped. In this case, a punch or a matrix made of metal, the second part is made of hard rubber. In hydraulic stamping, the workpiece is mounted on a detachable die and is large liquid or gas is supplied at pressure. As a result, the blank takes the form of a matrix.

Blast stamping is mostly rigid alloys, poorly deformable details made of the material are stamped. The essence of blasting stamping The blank is larger than gas or

liquid as follows matrix due to the force created by the pressure takes the form of a cavity. Zagotovka formed deforms rapidly due to the high energy When stamping spherical, complex, large items, stamping them inconvenient or the stamps will be too large in size and removable construction will be complicated. In this case, the items are stamped on the elements, then the pieces are welded. Here are three simple steps you can take to begin the process of preparation for mediation stamped and then welded. If production requires large quantities of metal products or blanks of the same sample, it is advisable to use the stamping method. Metal stamping is carried out from a deformable sheet material specifically shaped to the desired pressure. Metal stamping has been used since ancient times: many centuries ago, our ancestors made jewelry, weapons and household items in this way. Then it was done manually and at a much slower pace, but now the process is automated, and the production of a part takes much less time. For the production of flat and volumetric products with thin walls, sheet stamping is applied to the parts. It is carried out with or without special stamping and pressing. Divide into hot and cold. The method of hot processing is used in the production of bottom boilers, boats, shipbuilding elements. Gaps of 3-4 mm thickness are used. Composition drawings for parts, change of metal are taken into account: possible compression during beating or bending. It is carried out in order to minimize its illegal persistence. Cold stamping is more economical and progressive. This allows you to prepare specific parts, so it does not require tolerance, which means excessive spending

on materials. It is used in the production of small and large Products (Car Bodies, chassis, ship lining, elements of watches, etc.). For stamping, the following machines are used: vibration scissors, crank and dowel presses. Depending on the type of equipment, the separation and forming performance is distinguished. Manufacture of stamped parts for ordering. We provide stamping service for plastic metal parts, which ensures the execution of orders of non-standard parts and the release of large batches of the same types of products. For stamping plates (cold), we use a method of machining on perforated metal. Cold stamping is carried out without heating, as a result of which there will be no scale on the metal surface. With its help it is possible to obtain products of any exact size of the desired shape, with a smooth surface and abrasion-resistant qualities. A wide range of presses with a pressure of 2 to 160 tons allows stamping metal for any purpose. The press is equipped with roller and sleeper straps. Cold stamping has the ability to stamping metal to order for any accuracy and complexity, the thickness of the metal is from 0,7 to 8 mm. In modern industry, stamping is used for the

production of parts from 1mm to hundreds of tons and sizes from 1 mm to 10 meters. The technology of stamping metal parts of plastics requires special equipment: these are scissors, elbow press and dowel press, several washers and a matrix surface. It is also necessary to comply with the norms of work and the rules for calculating materials. Idravlik press for cold stamping is often used with reduced material consumption of different shapes, which makes it possible to produce different designs and parts that occur in the equipment. In addition, the choice of the press depends on the work that needs to be done with the workpiece. For example, for cutting and stabbing, simple movement presses are required, which is characterized by a slight slipping of slides and washers. To make a hood, you will need a press that will move twice and will significantly increase the volume of the slide and laundry. By design, the presses are single-cranky, double-edged, four-Edged, but they all differ in the presence of a matrix. The last two types differ in the size of the sleeves and sliders, which are larger in size.

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